

The practice of applying inclusive economic theory for economic development and poverty reduction.

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ABSTRACT

This article develops various methods for resolving economic crises and financial difficulties in the countries of the world. Nevertheless, the analysis shows that the most important way to save the region from poverty is to introduce inclusive economic institutions. Economically inclusive institutions create inclusive markets that not only allow people to pursue careers that best suit their skills, but also create a level playing field for everyone to pursue their careers. When owners can start their own businesses, workers can work more efficiently, less profitable businesses are replaced by competitive ones.

Keywords: companies, inclusive economy, competitiveness,

INTRODUCTION

Today it is no secret that countries lagging behind in economic development offer various economic opportunities to restore the economic situation. Nevertheless, we can say that these relief measures have actually reduced unemployment and poverty rates. The numerous local relief measures alone are not enough to achieve economic stability. Because we all know that it is impossible to achieve economic stability without carrying out the task of improving economic forecasts year after year, creating jobs and at the same time dealing with the problem of price levels.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

If we fully examine life in countries with a stable economy, we will be able to see that in most of them there is an institution of inclusive economics. An inclusive market does not just mean free markets. Looking back, there was a market in Barbados in the 17th century. At the same time, however, property rights on the island were available to only a handful of zamindars, not all, and the colony's markets were far from inclusive. The slave trade was one of the institutions that

systematically coerced the majority of the population and deprived them of the opportunity to choose their desired profession and their own abilities. Sustainable economic growth is almost always accompanied by technological changes that increase the efficiency of human labor, land and available capital. If we remember our ancestors who lived only a century ago, they did not have technologies such as water pipes, cooling systems and electricity, not to mention information technologies, robots and computer-based devices. It's hard to imagine that in the past most people struggled just to survive. In such a situation in the regions of Western Europe, history testifies that the great scientists who made these discoveries earned billions of dollars and donated new technologies to society. The reason for the low economic performance of most poor countries is the low level of education, economic institutions that do not encourage parents to educate their children, and the inability of the government to build schools, finance them, and support the dreams of parents and students. The no support policy is one of the biggest mistakes. In addition, there were many cases of poor education in the country, as well as the involvement of young people in forced labor. This leads to their inability to mobilize their own talents. In such underdeveloped countries, most people are deprived of the right to pursue their potential profession. Economic institutions that harness the potential of inclusive markets, promote technological innovation, invest in people, and mobilize the talents and skills of large numbers of people are critical to economic growth.

DISCUSSION

Due to differences in institutions, institutions, regulations that affect economic performance, and incentives that encourage people to work, economic development also differs between countries. Comparing teenagers in North and South Korea, what can we expect from their lives? People in the North grow up in poor or skilled jobs where the initiative and creativity typical of entrepreneurs are lacking. Most of the knowledge they are taught in school consists of open propaganda aimed at strengthening the legitimacy of the existing system. They don't even have modern

technology, let alone computers. After graduating from school, you are required to do military service for a period of ten years. Furthermore, North Korean teenagers know that markets where they can use their knowledge and use their savings to buy things they need or want are not allowed by law. They may not even be sure what rights they will have in the future. South Koreans, on the other hand, receive good education from a young age and are encouraged to work hard and excel in their chosen career. South Korea's economy is based on market relations based on private property. Young people in this region have the right to enjoy the fruits of their labor and dedication if they succeed as entrepreneurs or workers - to improve their living conditions, to get a car and to freely use medical services. For this reason, the economy of South Korea, like other countries in the world, belongs to the developed countries. Most immigrants in the world travel there regularly to find work. Analyzes around the world show that every year more than ten thousand unemployed people find suitable jobs and receive high salaries. It's no secret that these indicators are increasing every year. The focus is on strengthening the state's provision of quality education and comprehensive opportunities to reduce unemployment and poverty. In addition, the representatives of the region have set the goal of reducing the human factor through comprehensive use of the digital economy, bypassing the human factor. The fact that brands with a high position in the world's most developed market economy have located their small businesses in South Korea is a sign of the development of the economy in this country.

CONCLUSION

When solving the above problem, we should consider that political and economic institutions are expected to be the final decision of society in an inclusive manner and lead to economic development. Or they can be extractive and hinder economic growth. Where extractive economic institutions controlled by extractive political institutions that harm economic growth and even prevent it from growing are put in the way, the country will fall into crisis. The question of which institutions to choose, that is, what policies the established institutions pursue, represents the main question

in studying the reasons for the development or collapse of countries. Why did the policies of some countries lead to the creation of inclusive and economic institutions? Growth? In the past and today we need to know what reasons led to the introduction of extraction mechanisms, the policies of many countries that form the basis of economic development. The conclusion is that everyone should strive to build economic institutions that bring progress. Countries in the world spend all their capital to reduce poverty. The analysis shows that the main reason for the development is the high lime content. In addition, developed countries try to prevent unemployment by creating jobs by providing freedom and support to entrepreneurship. Modern technologies are at the heart of the development of strong and high-quality education. The motivating force for the activity is also education and training in professions and trades. That is why our country attaches great importance to vocational training when it comes to measures to combat poverty. “On additional measures aimed at attracting poor and unemployed citizens to entrepreneurship, increasing their employment and vocational training and ensuring employment of the population” dated August 11, 2020 PQ-4804 - On this issue, Resolution No was adopted. The main goal of the decision is to introduce a new system of vocational and entrepreneurship training for the poor and unemployed, to establish cooperation with the private sector in vocational training, to organize vocational and entrepreneurship training processes, and to implement additional measures to ensure employment of the needy population and disabled people. The implementation of the tasks set out in this decision is of great importance for preventing unemployment and reducing poverty in our country.

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